
89. A revolution in stellar astrophysics

IN ESSAY #76, I gave a summary of the contents of Data Release 3 (DR3), issued by the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium (DPAC) on 13 June. While DR3 covers just the first 34 months of mission data, it already contains 1.5 billion 5-parameter astrometric solutions.

But DR3 also includes a wealth of ‘extracted’ astrophysical data, which I summarise at the end of this essay. This is motivated by the fact that the chemical and physical characterisation of stellar spectra is essential for understanding the nature and evolution of stars and Galactic stellar populations. Observations from the ground over the past century have provided ‘only’ a very heterogeneous collection of chemical abundances for about two million stars in total, with fragmentary sky coverage.

The wealth of data now available from Gaia follows from the pre-launch mission optimisation, state-of-the-art space instrumentation, and rigorous processing and machine-learning classification techniques on ground; one person taking a mere 1 second to inspect every Gaia source, would require 200 years, working 8 hours a day!

THE TITLE OF this essay is taken from the presentation by Orlagh Creevey at the Sagan Summer Workshop in July. Orlagh leads Coordination Unit 8 of the Gaia DPAC which undertakes the source classification and ‘parameterisation’. This involves taking all relevant calibrated data, and extracting key astrophysical quantities based on automated classification techniques.

The 9 coordination units which today form the Gaia DPAC developed from various ‘working groups’ set up in the late 1990s... the preparatory and operational work has extended over more than 20 years! For most of this time, Coryn Bailer-Jones (MPIA, Heidelberg) led the CU8 work, with Orlagh Creevey (OCA, Nice) taking over its responsibility in June 2018. There are more than 70 contributors, including from Nice, Heidelberg, Bordeaux, La Coruña, Bruxelles, Athens, Catania, Madrid and Torino. The computations are executed in CNES, Toulouse.

Here I will provide the ‘big picture’ of the various parameterisation activities, aiming to cover more of the scientific results of this work in the future.

THE ‘ASTROPHYSICAL PARAMETERS’ included in Gaia DR3 provide the intrinsic properties of each stellar object (such as effective temperature, age, and chemical composition), as well as other inferred properties such as redshifts of distant sources and object classification.

CU8 does this by taking the mean (calibrated) BP and RP spectra, and the mean (calibrated) RVS spectra, along with astrometry (distances and proper motions) and photometry (G , G_{BP} , G_{RP}), and subjects all these to the ‘Astrophysical parameters inference system’ (Apsis).

Within this Apsis pipeline, described pre-launch by Bailer-Jones et al. (2013), 13 modules use different combinations of input data and/or models to produce astrophysical parameters for stars and sub-stellar objects, as well as galaxies and quasars.

THE OVERALL WORKFLOW is shown in the attached figure, which shows each of the 13 Apsis modules, colour-coded to show which of the input data sets are used to generate the output of each module. The details of these various modules, their outputs, and their validation, are described in a series of papers accompanying Data Release 3.

Details of the huge complexity underpinning Apsis are given in the three principal Apsis papers: Creevey et al. (2022) gives an overview of the Apsis methods and content, along with the detailed data products, and the associated 10 tables of the Gaia archive; Fouesneau et al. (2022) focuses on the stellar content (including parameter determination); and Delchambre et al. (2022) focusing on the non-stellar content.

Three other Gaia release papers are work module specific: Andrae et al. (2022) details the derivation of specific parameters from the photometry (GSP-Phot); Recio-Blanco et al. (2022) details the derivation of specific parameters from the RVS spectra alone (GSP-Spec); and Lanzafame et al. (2022) details the derivation of stellar chromospheric activity and mass accretion from the Ca II infrared triplet in the RVS spectra.

In the following, I will give a concise overview of these various modules to give the overall picture.

OF THE TWO ‘General Stellar Parameterizer’ modules, GSP-Spec uses projection and optimisation methods to best match the mean RVS spectra with a large grid of *theoretical* spectra computed using MARCS models, with a range of atmospheric parameters (T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, metallicity $[M/H]$, $[\alpha/Fe]$ and chemical abundances $[X/Fe]$), spanning the full parameter space of Galactic stellar populations (Recio-Blanco et al., 2022).

GSP-Phot estimates T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, $[M/H]$, absolute magnitude M_G , radius R , distance, line-of-sight extinctions (A_0 , A_G , A_{BP} and A_{RP}), as well as the reddening $E(G_{BP}-G_{RP})$ by forward-modelling the BP/RP spectra, apparent G magnitude, and parallax using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method.

OF THE VARIOUS ‘classifiers’, the Discrete Source Classifier (DSC) classifies sources probabilistically into five empirical classes (star, white dwarf, physical binary, quasar, galaxy).

The Unresolved Galaxy Classifier (UGC) estimates the redshift of unresolved galaxies. It does this by applying a supervised machine-learning model to their sampled BP/RP spectra.

The QSO Classifier (QSOC) aims to determine the redshift of sources that are classified as quasars by the DSC module. It is based on the cross-correlation between a rest-frame quasar template and an observed BP/RP spectrum, evaluated at a range of trial redshifts. The module predicts redshifts in the range $0.0826 < z < 6.1295$, along with the corresponding uncertainty.

The Multiple Star Classifier (MSC) infers stellar parameters by assuming that the BP/RP spectrum is a composite spectrum of an unresolved coeval binary system, and that the two components have a flux ratio in the BP/RP spectrum between 1–5.

The Total Galactic Extinction module (TGE) uses a subset of giants with extinction estimates provided by GSP-Phot as extinction tracers, to construct all-sky maps at various resolutions of the total Galactic foreground extinction.

IN THE OTHER PROCESSES, FLAME (Final Age and Mass Estimates) takes the output spectroscopic parameters from GSP-Phot and GSP-Spec, along with astrometry and photometry, to derive the evolutionary parameters: radius, luminosity, mass, and age.

ESP-CS computes a chromospheric activity index from the analysis of the RVS Ca II infrared triplet.

ESP-HS processes the BP and RP spectra, along with the RVS spectra when available, to provide a spectral type for all stars, and stellar parameters for $T_{\text{eff}} > 7500$ K.

ESP-UCD is dedicated to the analysis of ultra-cool dwarfs, and it produces T_{eff} for these stars.

Finally, ESP-ELS analyses emission-line stars, and provides class probabilities and labels, along with a measurement of the $H\alpha$ equivalent width.

THE NUMBERS derived by Apsis for Data Release 3 are quite staggering: source classification and probabilities for 1.6 billion objects; interstellar medium characterisation and distances for up to 470 million sources, including a 2-d total Galactic extinction map; and 6 million redshifts of quasar candidates and 1.4 million redshifts of galaxy candidates. The astrophysical parameters include many stellar spectroscopic and evolutionary parameters for up to 470 million sources.

These comprise T_{eff} , $\log(g)$, and $[M/H]$ (470 million using BP/RP; 6 million using RVS); radius (470 million), mass (140 million), age (120 million), chemical abundances (5 million), diffuse interstellar band analysis (0.5 million), activity indices (2 million), $H\alpha$ equivalent widths (200 million), and further classification of spectral types (220 million) and emission-line stars (50 000).

THESE CATALOGUES, based entirely on Gaia data, provide the most extensive homogeneous database of astrophysical parameters to date. As Chas Beichman, Director of the NASA Exoplanet Science Institute (NExSci) at Caltech, put it recently, ‘... [The next generation] will never know the struggle to determine a distance or a spectral type thanks to you and the Gaia team.’